

Topic: CIRC BIO-01-01 Circular Cities and Regions Initiative's project development assistance (CCRI-PDA)

D5.1 - Communication Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy – first draft

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D5.1 - Communication Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy – first draft

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Abstract	This deliverable contains the strategic planning of communication and dissemination activities throughout the DECISO project, starting by giving the project context; it continues by defining the objectives of communication and dissemination, providing a stakeholder analysis and deducing from this the communication matrix. The deliverable further describes the communication and dissemination channels and gives a list of the workshops and conferences to be held. It also includes internal management tools for communication and dissemination activities, as well as obligations under the Grant Agreement. Finally, it describes in detail the different tasks for the project partners sketched along the timeline of the project.
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1. DECISO Context

1.1. Project vision

Investment is the seed for growing a circular economy. The project 'DEvelopers of Circular SOLutions' (DECISO) will support European cities and regions to develop financing schemes for circular economy (CE) initiatives. DECISO partners will set up four pilot projects in Hamburg (DE), Alentejo (PT), Northwest Germany (DE) and West Macedonia (EL). The pilots will cover different sectors – waste, water, energy and agri-food. Integrating input from stakeholders along the value chain will allow the development of robust business plans. This, in return, shall foster the interest of investors and support from the local community.

DECISO uses an ecosystem approach: it will explore how circular economy business plans can be tailored to different geographical, economic, natural, and social environments. Based on this, DECISO will establish guidelines for financing schemes which other European cities and regions can use for their circular economy initiatives. DECISO is funded under the Horizon Europe program, which promotes research and innovation across the EU. Together with other Horizon Europe projects, DECISO will accelerate the green transition across Europe.

1.2. The pilots' programs

1.2.1 City Hamburg

Within DECISO, the City of Hamburg (FHH) will develop and implement financial schemes for circular economy at the city or sectoral level, by engaging, among others, finance institutions and partners. The goal is to mobilise investments from regional agencies, SMEs and industries that will complement the budget allocated to the circular economy through the Hamburg Climate Plan.

1.2.2 Alentejo

The Commission for Coordination and Regional Development of Alentejo (CCDRA) will support local authorities and their associations in the definition and development of financial schemes for circular systemic solutions in the agri-food sector.

1.2.3 Northwestern Germany

The Oldenburgisch-Ostfriesischer Wasserverband (OOWV), one of the largest water service providers in Germany, aims at exploring the potential of rainwater use in rural areas and to develop circular economy concepts such as water reuse.

1.2.4 Western Macedonia

The Municipal District Heating Company of the Wider Region of Amyntaio (MDHA) wants to implement a circular economy project that exploits biomass and residues/wastes and hereby prevents energy poverty.

1.3. Activities and impacts

Figure 1 Project phases and timeline of project implementation

DECISO will be implemented in different phases. A first set of activities (WP1) will serve to analyse the state of the art of the markets in the pilot areas. Furthermore, knowledge will be gathered and shared within the Consortium on existing financing schemes and good practices. Starting in parallel, another set of activities (WP2) will map and engage important stakeholders in the pilot areas. The goal is to establish working groups for each of the circular economy programs. Ultimately, these activities aim at fostering support among different stakeholders and ensuring political commitment to the programs. Based on the analysis carried out, the DECISO partners will develop technical solutions (WP3 and WP4), namely financing schemes and concrete business plans. The goal is also to develop operational services for different stakeholder groups involved in investment in CE projects. A last set of activities (WP5) aims at sharing information on DECISO with a larger set of stakeholders, including in other EU regions. Communication will also be two-sided, meaning engaging in a dialogue with different stakeholder groups. Last, the learnings and technical solutions developed will be exploited to develop guidelines that should incite other regions to replicate the adopted schemes and to get the stone rolling in the multiplication of CE programs.

1.4. Consortium Partners

The DECISO project is run by a consortium of 10 partners from 5 countries, representing 2 research organisations, 2 public authorities, 2 public suppliers, 3 private companies and 1 non-profit association.

Figure 2 DECISO Consortium

2. Communication and Dissemination

Communication and Dissemination activities will be led by ACR+, with the support of partners. Section 9 of this document shows the tasks of the Consortium partners and the points at which they get involved. This Strategy Document is accompanied by the Communication kit which contains the tools (templates, messaging, visual identity) that the Consortium will use in its Communication and Dissemination activities.

2.1. Objectives

Communication and Dissemination is a key element of the DECISO project, to build a strong ecosystem, involving all stakeholders, as described above. The ultimate objective is to create communities that support circular economy initiatives and contribute to their development. This shall in return promote political commitment.

Communication activities will aim at informing and raising awareness about the DECISO project and the larger topic of the circular economy. Information will be provided both targeting EU-wide stakeholders and local stakeholders. For the latter, the information will be tailored to emphasize activities in the pilots. In addition to raising awareness, communication activities will incite a dialogue with local stakeholders. Stakeholders shall be given a platform to ask questions, raise concerns and provide suggestions regarding the circular economy initiatives. The communication activities will provide several channels for such participation. In this sense, communication is strongly linked to stakeholder engagement (WP 2, Task 1). Communication activities will accompany the project from the beginning until the end.

In addition, dissemination activities will be used to present and discuss the technical results of the project in more detail. DECISO results will be, for example: insights from the analysis of the markets and regulatory framework, the financing schemes and business plans developed for the four pilots, policy recommendations and the guidelines and roadmaps for replication. Project results will be disseminated in different formats, such as scientific articles, workshops and conferences. The aim is to reach stakeholders who are interested in the (technical) details of the project or a pilot initiative. Dissemination activities will start after the first year of the project, when the first results (market analysis, existing best practices, literature review) are expected.

2.2. Target groups – stakeholder matrix

The first and most important step in preparing communication activities is to get a good understanding of the target groups/stakeholders¹. Two tools will help with this exercise: the Stakeholder Typology and the Stakeholder Matrix. These tools allow sorting stakeholders into groups based on different criteria and facilitate gaining an understanding of whom to target, how, and when.

The objective of the communication activities is to engage stakeholders in a way that positively impacts the project and its outcome. Furthermore, successful communication may avoid opposition towards the project. Pilot partners will reflect which persons or organisations for each of those groups are the most important stakeholders relating to their project; the same will be done for stakeholders at the EU level and for EU-wide upscaling by all project partners. Furthermore, the Consortium will pay particular attention to communicate with stakeholders from important sister projects – who can belong to various categories below. Such sister projects are those listed in Table 1.3. of the Grant Agreement, but also others, for example, other Horizon projects on circular economy. Table 1 below shows the different groups of stakeholders, what their interest in the project could be and what impact they could have on the project. There are, of course, overlaps and linkages between stakeholder engagement – which is subject to Task 2 – and communication and dissemination. Therefore, similar categories of stakeholders are used in D.2.1. and in this deliverable. To highlight the linkage, column 1 of Table 1 shows the categories used in the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy, and column 2 shows the respective categories used in the communication and dissemination strategy.

¹ 'Target groups' and 'stakeholders' are used interchangeably for this project.

Table 1 Stakeholder typology

Category in D. 2.1. (stakeholder engagement purpose)	Category in D.5.1. (communication and dissemination purpose)	Interest	Potential positive or negative impact
Public Administrations and Agencies	Local public authorities Public administration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welfare of citizens – ensure energy/water supply, clean city Acquire and manage EU or national funding Carry out rules 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In charge of organization/initiating CE projects Provide/restrict funding Issue/object to building permits Decide on actions of public utilities Can raise issues at the national level
	National and EU public authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Same as local PA Want to have a coherent approach throughout the country/EU 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Make the rules Provide funding (grants, loans) Provide expertise
Policy makers	Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The project(s) can give them publicity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> They can support/impede suggested CE projects (permissions, budget allocation) Can raise awareness and promote the project amongst citizens/ can incite citizens to oppose the project
Investors	Banks, Credit institutes, Angel Investors and Syndicates, Green Impact Hubs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Looking for profitable investment opportunities Focus on sustainability and environmental impact Focus on B2B and B2C circular economy sectors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invest in suggested CE projects, provide loans Help identifying new business opportunities Can foster environmental (green) and high social impact solutions They often require a solid, scalable business
Private sector and industry (consultancy, developers, services)	Enterprises, consultants/experts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business opportunity by providing services financed by local authorities Initially publicly funded projects may kick-start the development of new business strands Initial funding by local authorities can help them to develop innovative solutions – compete with other businesses Can also be customers in need of a resource produced by the initiative (e.g. water, energy) Can be providers of resources relevant to the initiative (e.g. biomass) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participate in talks and workshops May engage in PPP May carry out R&D for local solutions in the sector of interest Provide technical expertise Might not do a good job/ financially not viable As customers: define demand and prices As providers: define supply and prices
Civil society	Representatives of civil society (CSO), NGOs, industry associations (such as chambers of commerce)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Probably corresponds to their ideology/overall goals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Voters (individual citizens and representatives in local working groups etc.) (long-term impact) May campaign for or against a project/ mobilise citizens
Citizens	Citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Will directly be impacted by CE projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Voters (more of a long-term impact)

Category in D. 2.1. (stakeholder engagement purpose)	Category in D.5.1. (communication and dissemination purpose)	Interest	Potential positive or negative impact
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start citizen initiatives As customers, they may buy/use the product or not
Academia / Research Centres Spin-offs	Research organisations/Academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interested in technical results of DECISO 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dissemination Provide expertise
Media	Media/journalists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interested in stories Local media: when a program gets launched, a new initiative starts (but must be concrete) EU media: when there is an article about new legislation/policy on CE, pilots may serve as an example 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Impact citizens

The **Stakeholder Matrix** below maps the different stakeholders according to their level of interest and impact, to identify visually which are the most important groups to reach out to (core target group). The secondary target group is also important, of course, but may be reached through more punctual communication or dissemination activities. Note, however, that the roles of each target group and therefore their place in the matrix may vary between the pilot projects.

Figure 3 Stakeholder Matrix

2.3. Communication Matrix

The Table 2 summarises key aspects of the communication strategy: the key messages, the objectives and the communication channels for each target group. The key messages can, of course, be rephrased to fit the overall piece of communication, but the essence of the message should be included in the communication.

Table 2 Communication matrix

Target group	Key message	Objectives	Communication channels
Local or regional public administration	Promoting this circular economy project/circular economy will help our community become autonomous, resilient to crisis and grow. Let us discuss together how to create a supportive legal and financial framework for this project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acquire funding Get permissions for projects Achieve regulatory changes Use public utilities/suppliers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pilot workshops Pilot SH Working group PDA Management Team
National and EU public authorities	Our circular economy solution has a strong potential for stimulating social and economic growth and job creation, and to mitigate climate change in this city/region.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gain knowledge on financing opportunities Achieve regulatory changes, if necessary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU-level workshops and conferences Website, social media Direct outreach (email) using promotional material

Target group	Key message	Objectives	Communication channels
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Political support (e.g. creation of programs) Financing opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU media
Policymakers	Promoting this circular economy project/circular economy will help our community become autonomous, resilient to crisis and grow. This project will benefit your voters – join us to share your ideas on how to best advance it.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Achieve endorsement for the project – supportive voice in local government and towards citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pilot workshops Pilot SH Working group Direct outreach (email) using promotional material Local social media Local media Website
Banks; Credit Institutes, Angel Investors and Syndicates, Green Impact Hubs	Promoting this circular economy project/circular economy will help our community become autonomous, resilient to crisis and grow. Evaluating all new circular economy opportunities in a dynamic context (including mindset change of people, legislative framework, etc...) to face the climate change and its effects. Get on board to invest in a high-social and environmental impact initiative that will help our city/region flourish. Take a look at the potential business scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand the criteria to acquire financing Understand the needs of Angel Investors and Syndicates Finally, acquire loans, or funding or business partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct outreach (email) using promotional material Pilot workshops Small focused business pitches Local media, social media
Enterprises – as customers	This project will ensure the sustainable availability of the resource you need to continue your business.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand what they need Ensure they will use and buy the CE project's product 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct outreach (email) using promotional material Pilot SH Working Group Pilot workshops Local media, social media
Enterprises, consultants/experts – as service providers	Get on board to create a new product that will help our city/region flourish. Join our working team to seize this opportunity for innovation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get them to carry out or support the technical project implementation and creation of the product 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct outreach (email) using promotional material Pilot SH Working Group Pilot workshops Local media, social media
Representatives of civil society CSOs, NGOs, industry associations (such as chambers of commerce)	Promoting this circular economy project/circular economy will help our community become autonomous, resilient to crisis and grow. You are the voice to and from citizens – join us to share your ideas.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand what they want/need Foster support for the project and multiply engagement (e.g. through CSO campaign or their communication) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local media Pilot social media Pilot workshops Pilot SH working group Website
Citizens	Living in a cleaner environment with access to energy/water/... regardless of global crisis – it is possible. Come and find out about our project and share your ideas.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand what they need Ensure they will use and buy the CE project's product 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local media Pilot social media Website

Target group	Key message	Objectives	Communication channels
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise awareness and incite behavioural change regarding natural resource use 	
Researchers Organisations /Academia	Promoting this circular economy project/circular economy will help our community become autonomous, resilient to crisis and grow. Mutual exchange of learning and expertise will accelerate the green transition across Europe.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage in an exchange of experience • Get supported through their expertise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot and EU workshops and conferences • Website • Social media • EU and local media
Media/Journalists	This circular economy project/circular economy is innovative and will help our community become autonomous, resilient to crisis and grow. You are the voice to and from citizens – please share your activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incite to share DECISO press releases/news in the media • Invite to interview project officers/developers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Press release • Website • Social media

3. Communication channels

3.1. Website

The website with the following URL has been set up: <https://www.decisoproject.eu> . It has been designed by ACR+ with input from the partners (see section 8 'Responsibilities and Work Plan' of this document). CNR is responsible for the technical implementation and technical maintenance of the website.

ACR+ will update the website contents at least quarterly. Links to the website will be made in all social media and other communication channels, including informal ones (e.g., emails), by all project partners.

3.1.1 Content

The website is the general interface with stakeholders and reaches out to the largest range of stakeholders. It will provide general information about the DECISO project, its rationale and objectives, its activities and expected impacts. Furthermore, it will explain each of the pilot CE initiatives.

In addition to this general information, the website will have a section ('financing circular economy') going into more detail about the topic – circular economy and financing schemes. This section aims to place the project in the larger thematic context and to highlight which needs it addresses. This shall increase the legitimization of the EU investment in the DECISO project towards citizens. Therefore, the first three subpages explain the project context and the problem to be addressed; whereas the last three subpages focus on how the project addresses these issues (added value), by presenting the projects' results and impacts.

All information on the website pages shall be prepared in a user-friendly way, including as much visualisation as possible.

The website will also contain a section 'resources' which will be used as a depository for information material produced by the consortium, such as reports, factsheets, presentations, videos, and press releases.

Figure 4 Website structure

3.1.2. Language

The website is developed in English as the main language. The sections on the pilot initiatives will also be available in translated versions (DE, PT, EL).

The text on the landing page (Home) and the pages presenting the project and the pilots (DECISO project, pilots) is drafted in accessible, easily understandable language, avoiding jargon and technical terms. Where technical terms are used, they shall be explained in a box or by linking to another page (e.g., ‘circular economy’ will be explained in a dedicated section).

3.2. DECISO DE

A DECISO community (including stakeholders at different scales) will be established, mainly aiming to facilitate the stakeholders’ engagement, the discussion, and to promote the sustainability and exploitability of the outcomes. This community will include members from the local, national, and European levels. It will be organised as a community of interest that uses as its main channel a digital ecosystem: the DECISO Digital Ecosystem tool (DECISO-DE). It will be an interactive hub of all the other activities organised within the project and the other channels. It is synthetically described in the next session. CNR configured and manages DECISO-Digital Ecosystem on its secure servers (based on the previous experience of the BIOVOICES social platform - www.biovoices-platform.eu). The effects of communication channels can be amplified using a DECISO Digital Ecosystem tool (DECISO-DE) that aims to facilitate the different stakeholders' activities, their information, collaboration and engagement at different levels and scales. It aims to catalyse and organise the convergence of already existing networks, communities, and projects about the Circular Economy within an online sociotechnical environment that facilitates and stimulates the direct engagement of the different types of stakeholders identified, facilitating the upscaling of outputs and outcomes.

Indeed, the digital ecosystem is part of the overall ecosystemic approach used within the DECISO project, which implies the stakeholders' engagement at different levels and different scales in the face2face, virtual

and hybrid activities of the project, but also after the end of the project for exploiting the results and share experiences and the knowledge produced by the consortium.

DECISO-DE is complementary with respect to the information provided within the website of the project (information that DECISO makes available), as DECISO-DE provides the stakeholders with an interactive environment, facilitating active engagement, open dialogue, interaction and collaboration, while the website aims to inform about the project. The Website and the DECISO-DE can be accessed by the stakeholders in a unitary way as two parts of a whole. More information is in the deliverable "D2.1- Stakeholders' engagement strategy", and it will be accessible from DECISO Digital Ecosystem menu on the website.

As was also summarized in the deliverable "D2.1- Stakeholder engagement strategy", members of the DECISO-DE community can play a proactive role, reading and sharing news and managing events, such as workshops, conferences, webinars, etc. , with the related Agendas, links to online events, videos, images, documents, presentations and comments.

Filters are also available to select news and events based on different information such as the status (Upcoming, In progress, Finished), the start date, the last contribution date, or in alphabetical order (from A to Z or from Z to A).

Furthermore, the DECISO-DE allows you to access the user guide on its homepage via the "Jump to the user guide" button.

Figure 5: DECISO DE homepage with the button to the user guide

To fully exploit the potential of DECISO-DE as a communication, dissemination and knowledge sharing tool, in the second period, the project will work on:

- a) improving the usability of DECISO-DE by adding other filters, such as displaying contents grouped by one of the four DECISO pilots. This view allows to have a picture of the various activities of each

pilot during the project. Additionally, features will be made available in September 2024 to access information and documents shared within DECISO-DE via keywords;

b) exploring new search functionalities based on natural language processing

c) enriching the contents of DECISO-DE with a new section (by 2025) that contains good practices from DECISO and other projects on Circula Economy.

d) increasing the interest of a wider community in DECISO-DE by organizing webinars (every 4 months) starting from September 2024;

e) involving sister projects through an involvement campaign starting from the DECISO conference in October 2024 to invite them to share their events, contents and news on DECISO-DE. This plan will be updated every six months.

3.3. Social media

As a first step, social media will be used to raise awareness about the project and gauge interest and ideally involvement from stakeholders. Throughout the project, social media will be used for several purposes: (1) to inform about events and enable participation; (2) to inform about project results; (3) to incite action by target groups; (4) to incite dialogue with target groups (to a lesser extent with priority given to the DECISO Digital Ecosystem).

3.3.1. Channels

We will have a DECISO account on the following social media channels: X/Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and YouTube. Each channel will have different uses and goals, based on its specificities and trends, as summarized in the table below.

Table 3: Key channels

	Type of content	Main audience	Purposes
X	Events promotion Dissemination of key results Announcement of newsletters and reports Sharing of news related to DECISO	Local or regional public administration National and EU public authorities Policymakers Representatives of civil society CSOs, NGOs, industry associations (such as chambers of commerce) Researchers Organisations /Academia Media/Journalists	1 - 2
LinkedIn	Events promotion Dissemination of key results Announcement of newsletters and reports Sharing of news related to DECISO Call for contribution / engagement / action	Local or regional public administration National and EU public authorities Policymakers Banks; Credit Institutes Enterprises – as customers Enterprises, consultants/experts – as service providers Representatives of civil society CSOs, NGOs, industry associations (such as chambers of commerce) Researchers Organisations /Academia Media/Journalists	1 – 2 - 3 - 4
Facebook	Events promotion Dissemination of key results Announcement of newsletters and reports Sharing of news related to DECISO Call for contribution / engagement / action	Citizens Media/Journalists	1 – 2 - 3
YouTube	Recordings Event participation (a posteriori)	All	2

As shown by Table 3, the key channel for the project will be LinkedIn as it is more oriented towards a professional audience, gives more space to exchanges between users, and is the channel where most partners are present. In addition, marketing data show that the difference between the number of male and female users is smaller on LinkedIn and Facebook (X: 37% female vs 63% male; Facebook: 43.7% female vs 63.3% male; 42.8% female vs 57.2%)². Thus, prioritising LinkedIn will help to reach a more gender-balanced audience.

Social media channels will be used in conjunction with and as resonators of the DECISO digital Ecosystem where most interactions will be redirected to become a social media of its own between DECISO's partners, involved actors, and followers.

3.4. Channels management and content curation

ACR+ will oversee handling the social media accounts and ensuring their visibility (and through that the visibility of DECISO website and consequently activities and results). In a first place, it will consist of posting regular updates and reviewing/answering comments if necessary. Secondly, ACR+ will conduct a permanent monitoring of accounts on similar topics, resharing relevant posts and information, commenting to make links with DECISO, and tagging accounts that could be interested.

All partners will contribute to increasing DECISO's profile on social media not only by sharing the posts from their own channels but also by providing content and suggesting relevant publications. To facilitate information sharing, an Excel file has been set, available on the shared drive. In this file, partners indicate to ACR+ which content they would like to post, and ACR+ takes care of posting it.

Social media posts shall be drafted in simple and clear language and include visualisation and audiovisual content whenever possible. Furthermore, interactive tools (e.g., surveys) may be used.

The hashtag #DECISO_EU shall be used in all social media posts on channels where DECISO does not have an account, including local social media channels, otherwise the DECISO account should be tagged. Posts must always include a reference and link to the DECISO website.

Partners are also highly encouraged to post about DECISO on their own channels. A guide has been created and is available on the share drive (Annex 6) to accompany them in the process. It gives access to the key tools to use, include instruction and tips on the role as a DECISO partners, and lists some relevant accounts to tag.

3.4.1. Newsletter

5 newsletters will be published throughout the project – one in the first year and two in the second and third years, respectively. These newsletters will announce and summarise the results of project events, activities, and results. They will include a general section and a section for each pilot initiative. Furthermore, they will include links to external information sources if relevant (e.g., other projects, academic articles). The

² <https://explodingtopics.com/blog/x-user-stats>

newsletters will be distributed through the mailing list and be available on the website for download. The newsletters will primarily be targeted at stakeholders working in the field of circular economy, but also journalists and any other stakeholders interested in the project.

3.4.2. Mailings

A mailing list will be developed by gathering contacts through pilot engagement activities, as well as through a subscription function on the website. Mails will be sent to inform the recipients about upcoming events and possibilities for the subscription. The list will also be used to distribute the newsletter and to disseminate reports. The mailing will be targeted, and the list may be limited to a certain group (e.g., if a conference targets only a certain group of stakeholders, or if participation is limited). Attention will be paid not to overload recipients with information, to avoid information fatigue.

The email contact for the project is: deciso.coordinator@irpps.cnr.it.

3.4.3. Partners' channels

The Consortium partners will use their social media channels and websites to communicate about the project. Communication content will be aligned with the overall strategy in terms of timing and visual identity. However, the content and format will be tailored to the respective target audiences. The visual identity shall be respected, and all communication (online posts, emails, etc.) shall include a link to the website. ACR+ will stay in close exchange with the partners through the Communication Working Group and ensure that partners' communication activities are in line with the overall strategy. A list of partners' channels is provided in Annex 1.

The pilot partners' communication activities will mainly target local and regional, but also national stakeholders. The social media objective '(3) incite action' (see section 3.2.) is particularly relevant for those pilots where the success of the program relies also on changes in the behaviour of certain target groups (e.g., separating waste).

3.5. Media relations

Media is an important channel to inform the public about the project. At the beginning of the project, a list of the most important media and their respective target group will be established, for EU-level communication and each of the four pilots. Subsequently, contacts with journalists will be established and maintained throughout the project. A contact list will be created with several groups of journalists (EU-wide communication; national; local level for the pilots).

To incite journalists to report on the project, the Consortium partners will draft press releases about important events and project results. Other possibilities for engaging with media include interviews or sharing audiovisual content. To avoid information overflow, it is important to reserve media contacts for the most interesting content.

ACR+ will make a list of relevant European affairs media that shall be contacted for press releases which synthesise project results and address an EU-level target group. Additionally, pilot partners will be responsible for sharing their press releases with local media

4. Dissemination channels

The Consortium will disseminate project results through the channels mentioned above (3 ‘Communication channels’). In addition, scientific reports will be disseminated through scientific journals, open access platforms for research studies (such as ResearchGate) and presentations at external conferences; furthermore, two conferences will be organized in 2023 and 2024 with stakeholders from EU regions to present and discuss project results; local workshops in each pilot area at the launch of the programmes and the end will also serve as dissemination platforms.

Annex 2 provides an indicative and preliminary list of databases, journals and conferences where DECISO results could be disseminated.

5. Workshops and Conferences

A series of workshops and conferences will be organized in the realm of the DECISO project. Face-to-face communication is still one of the best means to convey important information and engage people. Two conferences will be organized specifically for dissemination purposes, at the launch of the pilot programmes in month 12 and the end of the project in month 36. They will take place in Brussels and reach out to stakeholders from across the EU to inform and discuss with them the project. Furthermore, several other workshops will be organized in other Work Packages and tasks. They have specific goals but also serve communication with stakeholders. Annex 3 shows all DECISO Workshops and Conferences.

Furthermore, DECISO partners will attend and showcase the project at national and international events and in particular events within CCRI and DECISO will participate in the CCRI working groups activities.

6. Monitoring and reporting

6.1. Internal monitoring tools and processes

All consortium partners shall keep track of their communication and dissemination activities and regularly report them to ACR+. ACR+ will then compile this information for the project reporting. The partners will monitor outreach as much as possible by using the website and social media statistics, keeping track of persons invited to workshops and the number of participants, etc. ACR+ will upload a tracking tool to Teams – the Table 4 indicates the structure of this tool:

Table 4 Tracking tool to monitor communication and dissemination activities

Workshops and conferences						
Activity	Date and location	Organiser	Target group	No. of persons invited	No. of participants	Other outputs
.....						
.....						
Social media activities						
Post	Date	Site visits	No. of shares		Comments on post	
.....						
Website activities						
Post	Date	Site visits		No. of shares		
.....						
Media work						
Activity	Outreach (e.g. press/media agency uptake, journalist enquiries)					
.....						
Dissemination activities						
Activity	Date	Author			Outreach	
.....						

6.2. Key Performance Indicators

Based on the grant agreement, the following indicators need to be reached to demonstrate successful communication and dissemination:

Table 5 Key Performance Indicators for Communication and Dissemination activities

Tool	Target audience	KPI	By when?
Scientific publications (open access) and conference presentations	Researchers, academics, policymakers, enterprises, financial actors and citizens	Min. 6 peer-reviewed publications, reaching a minimum of 500 people of the target audience	End of project
Annual conferences in yr. 2 and 3	Researchers and academics	Min. 200 participants in total	Yr. 2 and 3
Open Data, Open Access and Open Source results	Researchers, academics, policymakers, enterprises, financial actors and citizens	Min. 100 downloads in the last 12 months of the project	End of project
DECISO website and social media	Researchers, academics, policymakers, enterprises, financial actors and citizens	Min. 12 000 web visits/year, min. 42 000 cross-linking with social media accounts, referencing and SEO	End of project
Internal Communication Training	Consortium partners	2 trainings for min. 20 persons to increase outreach success by partners by 50-100% (take-up of press releases and impressions of social media posts by partners)	
Promotional Content (printed and online): 1 leaflet, 4 Brochures in the pilot areas (one per pilot), 5+ postcards, 6 infographics, 4 fact-sheets (one per pilot), 5 roll-ups (1 for the project and 4, one per pilot area) and posters.	Researchers, academics, policymakers, enterprises, financial actors and citizens	Min. 10 000 stakeholders reached through promotional actions	See Table 6, Work Plan
Journalistic content	Media outlets, associations, citizens	Min. 8 interviews (two per pilot area), min. 8 press releases (2 per pilot area), 5 newsletters	Interviews and press releases (see Table 6) Newsletters: 1 in yr 1, 2 in yr 2, 2 in yr 3

7. Exploitation Strategy

Exploitation means to “take action to use project results for commercial purposes, to tackle societal problems or in policymaking” ([Horizon Europe Guidelines](#))

Foreword

DECISO is not a company, nor is it an NGO or a public body. But as an EU project, we bring beneficiaries from different categories to work together toward a common cause - to make circular economy plans more effective and attractive. The common objective notwithstanding, partners have different exploitation priorities when it comes to project results, which too are quite different, ranging from scaling up solutions, stakeholders’ engagement, to any used technical tool. This makes business planning at the project level particularly challenging.

The extent to which individual interests can be pursued depends in no small part on IPRs, licensing schemes and conditions for free/open-source distribution of our validated strategies and approaches to pilot scaling, all of which can make exploitation more or less successful. The sooner partners manage to resolve these issues, the better. The goal of this strategy is to start smoothing this risk and elaborating on the exploitation deliverables. It ought to clarify who owns what with regard to intellectual property, so as to avoid any potential disputes in the future.

The Grant Agreement rules already take into account at high-level IPRs management. Notwithstanding that most of the results could be provided as open access to which to add each partner’s consultancy services, the situation could be unclear as regards any technical tools and third-party data stored on them. We need to pave the way for a clear understanding, also because future success also depends on the quality of products, services, tools, and frameworks we’re going to offer to customers.

7.1. The initial exploitation plan and its role in the DECISO’s framework

The overarching exploitation goal is to outline the DECISO project’s exploitable results and the key partners involved. In this first phase, we focus on a procedural plan for gathering information, barriers and opportunities so to provide the consortium, during the project progress, with a realistic framework for relevant results to be exploited by project partners.

The elements needed to deploy and exploit DECISO results and **create an impact beyond the project implementation** shall be built into the whole project concept. The engagement with other projects and initiatives, as well as with experts, territories and citizens will play a fundamental role in having wide outreach and preparing the ground for a complete and satisfactory exploitation.

Therefore, the exploitation plan leverages the concept of the DECISO extended network with the aim to:

- sustain and extend impacts reached with the project,
- ensure the widest utilisation of project results and spread of word about their benefits,
- provide a support network for local authorities and professionals in the areas of CE and environmental sustainability, with a set of guidelines enabling and encouraging solutions scaling and interdisciplinary cooperation when necessary. These guidelines can be used to ease recruitment to the network of organizations willing to promote the DECISO approach across Europe at both local and regional scales, and thereby provide a connected cluster for CE.

The exploitation of DECISO's results will be performed by project partners, but it will be a process involving several other external organisations, and public and private actors. They will be engaged and addressed by several activities and through all the DECISO's assets, communication, and cooperation initiatives.

Circular Economy requires the involvement of a wide range of actors – from the highest levels of government to civil society groups, from institutions to developers, or from entrepreneurs to marginalized social groups and young people, as well as future generations.

In order to understand why and how these actors intervene in the CE enhancement, we need to start from one fundamental presupposition, that the protection of the environment and its resources is a "common good". This universality concept implies that global concerns should be addressed where citizens live (i.e., at the local level), and deployed at the international level, like climate change, armed conflict, and cultural heritage. As such, it can be strongly argued that circular economy requires specific governance models that can adequately address and manage the territorial commons.

This, in turn, calls for collaborative approaches that offer proactive roles to all types of users. This strategy holistically addresses diverse objectives and priorities that can lead to better results in practices and strategies to implement them.

It is worth noting that the roles and responsibilities of the actors often vary between territories and different cultural, political, geographical, historical, and economic contexts. In fact, there is no one common approach or governance model for the use of Circular Economy.

The initial exploitation strategy consists of five main steps:

1. **understand the partners' requests and elicit the stakeholders' needs through the survey** (ref. the questionnaires in annexes 4-5)
2. **aggregate all the interviews and analyse / map the territorial needs:** Different partners are expected to have different targets and approaches. This is due to the peculiar territorial boundaries that drive the interest of each partner towards tailored exploitation paths. This heterogeneity can be accounted for by the flexibility of the DECISO's assets and the capability to scale some digital resources and methodological procedures.
3. **Analysis of DECISO's assets, the grounding IPRs, and replicability or scalability to other contexts.** It will leverage a benchmark between the DECISO's solutions' effectiveness (measured during the piloting campaign), and the territorial needs, also considering the performances of other existing solutions and CE frameworks.
4. **Draft exploitation paths and recommendations / guidelines.** DECISO's partners will deploy the validated assets to achieve a list of exploitation targets. All of them contribute to the medium- and long-term sustainability of the project's results and ensure that the planned impact on the local and territorial circular economy will be achieved. The details for exploitation targets will be defined in the second half of the project. As a minimum requirement, they will include **a)** the list of scalability and exploitability of our assets, **b)** the stakeholders' engagement in sustainability activities, and **c)** the preliminary agreements with third parties for replication.
5. **Draft a matrix for DECISO's replication and feasibility, also considering the stakeholders' feedback.** The assets produced within DECISO and shared in the exploitation phase will raise the interest of many heterogeneous stakeholders. Each of them will be addressed by one or more of the following activities: Consultancy and Advice, Training, Networking, and Financial analysis. Due to the

heterogeneity of the consortium’s participants and the DECISO stakeholders and, more in general, CE domains, we list below several different actions that will be included in our exploitation plan. They have been classified into three different streams: **A)** Enhance territorial recycling system; **B)** Maintenance of pilots’ validated solutions and sustainability models; **C)** Ensure sustainability in the medium and long term and sharing of good practices.

7.2. DECISO exploitation survey

The first step of our exploitation plan is to understand the replication potentialities of validated solutions and start flavouring the stakeholders’ interest in the proposed DECISO’s outcomes plan.

For this purpose, the consortium will use two questionnaires as tools to elicit information from internal (annex 4, only for piloting partners) and external sources (annex 5, only for stakeholders to be engaged). The latter will be deployed as an online survey.

Based on the outcomes of these questionnaires, the idea is to start analysing alternative solutions, so to be ready for a cursory benchmarking overview. If we really want DECISO to be exploitable beyond its lifetime, we should consider the right development, refining, and improvements to our key exploitable results (KERs).

Based on the deliverables indicated in the GA that are suitable for exploitation (see Table 6 below), the following DECISO KERs will be developed:

- CEE Strategy for Stakeholders' engagement. An easy-to-read document that extracts and outlines guidelines on how to replicate the DECISO Circular Economy Ecosystem approach in other urban and regional contexts for mobilizing and engaging stakeholders.
- CEE co-design approach for developing circular economy projects. Easy to read document that extracts and outlines guidelines on how to replicate the DECISO Circular Economy Ecosystem approach in other urban and regional contexts for co-design circular economy projects.
- Portfolio of sustainable practices, processes, business models, financing schemes, increased awareness of successful, concrete, replicable and customizable examples of innovative and sustainable financing schemes, processes and business models, well-functioning in operational environment and high replicability potential.

Additional KERs may be identified during the project life.

Table 6 DECISO deliverables feeding into to be KERs

Name of the result	Target group	Month of delivery
D.1.1 Market state of the art of circular economy in the pilot areas	Internal & external	12
D.1.2 Guide to good practices and opportunities at the European and national level	Internal & external	10
D.1.3 Reports from mobilisation and mutual learning workshops in the pilot areas	Internal	18
D.2.3 Lessons learned and policy recommendations from circular economy pilots	Internal & external	32
D.3.1 Local programmes for fostering circular economy	Internal& external	18
D.3.2 PDAs implementation models, operational services, and financing schemes	Internal& external	21
D.3.3 Potential risks and legal aspects of Programmes and PDAs	Internal& external	21

D.3.4 Sustainability and comparative analysis of pilots' experiences	Internal& external	36
D.4.2 Launch strategies from the pilots	Internal& external	22
D.5.7 Roadmap for DECISO scale-up	External	36
D.5.8 First CCRI-CSO policy brief	External	18
D.5.9 Second CCRI-CSO Policy Brief	External	36

To improve the impact of potential results, we must ensure that the stakeholders we engage are people who do not just have high interest, but also have high influence over policy processes. As to the framework itself, we should clarify to potential adopters whether it is meant for experienced professionals or foresight newbies; how much time and effort would be required to implement it in a new context; and perhaps provide a “lean” version of the strategies via online tools to those on low budgets and/or those who may be experiencing other resource constraints.

7.3. Further exploitation actions

Using the results of the surveys, the following exploitation and upscaling actions will be undertaken according subsequently:

- Promote the use of DECISO **results** obtained in the piloting areas:
 - Best practices (ways to engage stakeholders; research on the market state of the art;
 - Novel models (models for analysing local programs; PDA implementation models; model for cross-sectoral benchmarking; technical solutions for resource treatment (e.g. rainwater treatment));
 - Business models and financing schemes.
- Organise two workshops in Brussels aiming to create an interaction and discussion respectively with sister projects, and international and local stakeholders from different regions
 - Workshops aim also to build consensus about the project results
- Defining collaboration protocols with other networks
- With the aim to attract more private investors, the strategy will include three main steps:
 - A small survey at the beginning of piloting experiences (September-October 2024) with the goal of eliciting private investors' interest in DECISO's solutions, and potential additional factors enabling private business efforts. If possible, this survey will be performed during a targeted workshop, online or in presence in Brussels and, depending on the number of engaged participants, it could also include a brainstorming session on future opportunities. Nevertheless, we consider the option to leverage existing bigger events, such as CCRI workshops (Making circular investments pay off for cities and regions – 13th November 2024)
 - Build pitches for each pilot and – if needed – for different target private stakeholders (i.e. banks or angel investors). The pitches will be based on the actual business and sustainability performances monitored during the piloting activities.
 - Organise or attend a follow-up event with these stakeholders to discuss the actual potentialities, existing gaps, and next steps needed for making reasonable private investments in the circular economy sectors defined by DECISO's PDAs. Potential events to be joined include:

- Basque Circular Summit 2025, Bilbao (ES), 02-04 April 2025
- Responsible Investor Europe 2025. London (UK), June 2025
- ...
- Sign at least 4 Memoranda of Understanding with other local or regional authorities or public utility companies
- 1 Workshop in Brussels to assess potentialities, sustainability and replicability and EU level to facilitate scale-up
 - Output is a codified roadmap to facilitate replicability.

Further tasks and related KPIs will be developed downstream of the project steering committees and will feed into updated versions of the project exploitation plan.

8. Obligations

8.1. Acknowledgement of EU funding

Project-related communication and dissemination materials of all types and all communication materials, dissemination activities and any outputs of DECISO (articles, project websites, presentations, flyers, press releases, videos, etc.), must always display prominently the EU emblem and funding statement, stating the funding received from the European Union through Horizon Europe. Article 38.3 of the GA clarifies that if a beneficiary is in breach of any of its obligations on its communication activities, the grant may be reduced.

Please pay attention that the EU emblem (i.e. the EU flag) is NOT the logo of the European Commission or any other logo from an EU institution. Add the following funding statement next to the official EU emblem (in local languages, where appropriate): Funded by the European Union.

The EU emblem and funding statement can be downloaded here (in several languages): https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en

**Funded by
the European Union**

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

Furthermore, any reports or documents written about or in the context of the project must include the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

8.2. Protection of personal data

The consortium recognises the importance of the protection of personal data of those involved in communication and dissemination activities and takes great care in ensuring the above-mentioned activities are conducted in line with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation (EU) 2016/679). Any project activity involving people whose personal data are collected must comply with the EU and national regulations on data protection, as stated in article 15 of the [Grant Agreement](#). People registering to the DECISO mailing list and to public events will be asked to agree with the DECISO privacy policy that will explain what data is collected, how it is stored, and how these data will be used. Any participant in workshops or conferences will be asked to sign an informed consent form. The anonymized information gathered during these meetings will be interpreted and processed for publicly available project reports, when necessary. It will only be used for the DECISO project, and will not further be used for other purposes unless participants explicitly agree. The personal contact information will be collected purely for communication, dissemination and reporting purposes.

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European Union**

If pictures, recordings, or videos are taken during the DECISO activities and events, participants will be informed beforehand and given the possibility to refuse to have their images shared publicly.

8.3. Open Access to scientific publications

As stated in Annex 5 – Specific Rules to Art.17 of the [Grant Agreement](#), “beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results”. Scientific partners must refer to this article regarding the specific obligations regarding the publication, the open access, and the metadata to be used.

9. Responsibilities and Work Plan

The Table 7 below shows at which point of the project who are the partners that are required to carry out communication and dissemination activities. The cells in grey indicate workshops or conferences. The outputs below shall be announced on partners' social media channels when relevant, always including a link to the website.

Where partners are required to create content, ACR+ will send a reminder and, if necessary, a template 3–4 weeks (if possible) to the respective partners. ACR+ will review any content prepared by partners for the website to ensure harmony in style and language.

The partners are responsible for translating into their national language any content to be shared on the website's pilot pages and their local social media, as well as content prepared for media outreach (press releases).

Table 7 Communication and Dissemination Work Plan and Consortium partners' actions

	Time	Project outputs to communicate	Partners' communication activities
Nov22-Apr23	Apr 23	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ACR+: prepare the template for general pilot description; prepare templates for brochure (general info on pilots); prepare social media posts Pilot partners: draft text on projects based on templates by ACR+; prepare info on how to participate in working group; share on pilot social media Other partners: share on social media info and links to the website
	May 23	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU level Workshop: identification and discussion of good practices; how experts of CE and from sister projects can provide support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ACR+: organize workshop ACR+: Report from the workshop ACR+: share results on the website, and social media All the other partners: share results on social media and their channels
May23-Dec23	June 23	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National participatory workshops in pilots 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pilot partners: organize workshops ACR+: announce on pilot pages, on the DECISO Website, on the DECISO Digital Ecosystem and social media, such as Facebook, etc. Pilot partners: announce on local social media Pilot partners: Report from the workshop All the other partners: share results on social media and their channels
	Aug 23	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Good practices at the EU and national level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PDM, IRRADIARE and ACR+: draft first content for website sections 'good practices' and 'challenges to financing CE' All partners: will share this page within their website, channels and social networks
	Oct 23	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Market state of the art of CE in the pilot areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ACR+: prepare the template for #1 factsheet for each pilot – distribute via the website; newsletter Pilot partners: prepare content for #1 factsheet – distribute via local social media

	Time	Project outputs to communicate	Partners' communication activities
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other partners: announce #1 factsheet on social media with a link to the website • ACR+: Website: news re. market state in pilots • CCDRA and ACR+: Draft content for website section 'market state of the art in the pilots'/page 'results' • All partners: Press releases, social media communication on results
	Oct 23	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder's Working Groups per pilot 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot partners: Announce on website/social media, on the DECISO Digital Ecosystem, update pilot pages
	Dec 23	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production of the newsletter #1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACR+: Newsletter #1 produced, and shared on the website and with the social network • All partners: share the newsletter within their channels and the Social networks
	2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in CCRI events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All partners: sharing the discussion and results within the CCRI community during their events
Nov23-Apr24	M8-M19 (TBD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobilisation and mutual learning workshop in pilot 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot partners: organize workshop • Pilot partners: announce and summarise results for pilot channels but also to be shared in other regions and to be upscaled at the international level • Pilot partners: Report from the workshop • All partners: share results on social media and their channels
	May '24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop output: increase awareness among stakeholders, identify financial supports, identify legislative framework 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACR+/review by all partners: prepare the template for #2 factsheet • Pilot partners: prepare content for #2 factsheet • ACR+: update pilot pages on the website • ACR+: Report from the workshop • All partners: share results on social media and their channels
	April '24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review workshop: analysis of existing financing schemes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot partners: announce and summarise results for pilot channels but also to be shared in other regions and to be upscaled at the international level

	Time	Project outputs to communicate	Partners' communication activities
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot partners: Report from the analysis • All partners: share results on social media and their channels
May24-Oct24	May '24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local programs: SWOT, objectives, roles of local actors, competitive elements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Results to go into #2 factsheet • ACR+: Website - announcement on main page, update pilot pages • Pilot partners: Press Release, pilot social media
	May '24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up of managing teams for PDA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Results to go into #2 factsheet • ACR+: update pilot pages
	June '24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production of newsletter #2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACR+: Newsletter #2 produced, and shared on the website and with the social network • All partners: share the newsletter within their channels and the Social networks
	July '24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PDA implementation models: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Actions in each pilot ○ Actors involved in PDA ○ Timing, deadlines, milestones ○ Necessary operational services ○ Qualitative and quantitative indicators ○ Monitoring and evaluation strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Results to go into #2 factsheet • ACR+: Website - announcement on the main page, update pilot pages, sharing in the DECISO Digital Ecosystem
	July '24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specification of financing schemes - potential risks and legal aspects, risk management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PDM/CCDRA: prepare content for the Website: section 'financing CE'/ page 'results' • OV/pilot partners/ACR+: prepare #1 infographic (1 per pilot, 1 general) • All partners: will share the infographics within their website, channels and social networks
	Aug/Sept '24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot info days, launching the programs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot partners: Necessary infrastructure: newsletter, webpage, Q&A online and phone service, documents describing the program, factsheets • Pilot partners: press release for local media; communication on social media • ACR+: press release for EU media; social media posts
	Aug/Sept '24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One Dissemination Workshop per pilot 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACR+: Announcement website – main page and pilot pages and the DECISO Digital Ecosystem

	Time	Project outputs to communicate	Partners' communication activities
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot partners: press release for local media; communication on social media • Pilot partners: Report from the workshop • All partners: will share the results using their channels, website and social networks
	Aug/Sept '24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch Call for projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot partners/ACR+: Website - Publish the call on the pilot pages and social media, on pilot channels and in newspapers, and on the websites of the pilot organisations.
	Oct '24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual Conference for Dissemination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All partners: disseminate the news of the conference within their websites, channels and Social media • ACR+: summarise and share results on the website, the DECISO Digital Ecosystem, and social media
	Nov '24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploitation Workshop in Brussels: discussing experiences; create consensus around results and best practices in the pilot areas; Define collaboration protocols; establish MoU (T.5.3) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACR+/OV: Report from the workshop • ACR+/OV: summarise and share results on the website, social media
	2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in CCRI events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All partners: sharing the discussion and results within the CCRI community during their events
Nov24-Apr25	Dec '24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production of newsletter #3 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACR+: Newsletter #3 was produced, and shared on the website and with the social network • All partners: share the newsletter within their channels and the Social networks
	Apr '25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploitation Workshop in Brussels with SH who sign MoU (at least 4): document feedback/uptake, input for codifying a roadmap to facilitate replicability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACR+/OV: summarise and share results on the website, social media • ACR+/OV: press release on results of exploitation workshops • ACR+/OV: Report from the workshop
	May '25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production of newsletter #4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACR+: Newsletter #4 produced, and shared on the website and with the social network • All partners: share the newsletter within their channels and the Social networks
May25-Oct25	June '25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roadmap for DECISO scaling up 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACR+: Publish Roadmap on Website/social media

Time	Project outputs to communicate	Partners' communication activities
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All partners: will share this roadmap within their website, channels and social networks
Aug '25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grant agreements signed for each pilot 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ACR+: Website: update on pilot pages and, and general news Pilot partners: Press releases for local media, social media and on the DECISO Digital Ecosystem
Aug '25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lessons learned and replicability of DECISO 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OV/ACR+: prepare content for the website section 'multiplication'/ page 'results' and the DECISO Digital Ecosystem All partners: will share this page within their website, channels and social networks
Aug '25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business planning guide with different business models developed by DECISO 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ACR+: Announce and share on the website, and social media with a link to the guide ACR+: press release KOYS/ACR+: #2 Infographic 'the guide in a snapshot' Pilot partners: social media communication, the DECISO Digital Ecosystem and press release sharing the guide All partners: Announce and share on their channels, website, and within social media the link to the guide
Oct '25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> One Dissemination Workshop per pilot 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pilot partners: summarise and share results on the website, and social media and produce a Report from the workshop
Aug '25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comparative analysis of pilot's experiences for their scalability Model for cross-sectoral benchmarking/ benchmarking 4 pilots 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KOYS: Prepare content for website section 'multiplication'/ page 'results' KOYS/ACR+: #3 Infographic cross-sectoral benchmarking
Sept '25 (alt. with other conferences)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Annual Conference for Dissemination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All partners: disseminate the news of the conference within their websites, their channels and Social media ACR+: summarise and share results on the website, and social media

	Time	Project outputs to communicate	Partners' communication activities
	Oct 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production of newsletter #5 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All partners: summarise and share results on the website, social media ACR+: Newsletter #5 produced, and shared on the website and with the social network All partners: share the newsletter within their channels and the Social networks
	2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participation in CCRI events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All partners: sharing the discussion and results within the CCRI community during their events

10. ANNEX

Annex 1: Partners' channels

Table 8 Partners' channels table

Partner name	Communication channel (type, name, link)
OOWV	Website: https://www.oowv.de/wissen/wasserschutz/projekte/ LinkedIn: https://de.linkedin.com/company/oowv Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/mein.oowv/ Facebook: https://de-de.facebook.com/meinoowv/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@oowv6885
KOYS	Website: http://www.koyslab.eu/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/koys-srl/about/ Twitter: @fnpolicy
PDM/UoWM	Website: Πανεπιστήμιο Δυτικής Μακεδονίας (uowm.gr) LinkedIn: University of Western Macedonia LinkedIn Twitter: Πανεπιστήμιο Δυτικής Μακεδονίας (@uowm) / Twitter Facebook: Πανεπιστήμιο Δυτικής Μακεδονίας Kozáni (facebook.com) YouTube: hΠανεπιστήμιο Δυτικής Μακεδονίας - YouTube
MDHA	Website: ΔΕΤΕΠΑ – Δημοτική Επιχείρηση Τηλεθέρμανσης Ευρύτερης Περιοχής Αμυνταίου (detepa.gr)www.detepa.grw.detepa.gr Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/detepa.amindeo
FHH	Website: Europa - EU - Europäische Union - Hamburg in Europa - hamburg.de Facebook: Hamburger Senat - Startseite Facebook Twitter: Hamburger Senat (@Senat_Hamburg) / Twitter Instagram: Hamburger Senat (@senat_hamburg) • Instagram-Fotos und -Videos YouTube: HamburgerSenat - YouTube
OV	Website: www.ovaerdi.com LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/officinaeverdi/mycompany/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/officinae.verdi/ Twitter: https://mobile.twitter.com/ovgroupspa YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCj0HEPNQHKcnBFudWYtDTdA (@officinaeverdi)
IRRADIARE	Website: https://www.irradiare.com/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/irradiare LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/irradiare?trk=company_logo Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/irradiare-science-forevolution/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/irradiare-science-forevolution/
CCDR	Website: Comissão de Coordenação e Desenvolvimento Regional do Alentejo (ccdr-a.gov.pt) Twitter: CCDR Alentejo (@ccdralentejo) / Twitter Facebook: CCDR Alentejo Évora Facebook YouTube: CCDR Alentejo - YouTube
CNR	Website: Home Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – IRPPS (www.irpps.cnr.it) DECISO Digital Ecosystem: https://www.decisoproject.eu/deciso-ecosystem/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/consiglio-nazionale-delle-ricerche (Twitter: CNR Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (@CNRSocial) / Twitter Facebook: CNR Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche Facebook

	Publication/s on international journals to be selected
ACR+	Website: http://acrplus.org Twitter: https://twitter.com/ACRplus Linkedin: ACR+ Association of Cities and Regions for sustainable Resource management LinkedIn

Annex 2: List of dissemination channels

Dissemination Channels
• ResearchGate ResearchGate Find and share research
• Cordis
• Local press publications in all regions
• Ecomondo
• CCRI conferences
• International Journals
• Horizon Magazine
• Horizon Results Booster
• Horizon Results Platform
• Open Research Europe

Annex 3: DECISO Workshops and conferences

Table 9 Deciso Workshops and conferences

Workshop/Conference and related task	Target group	Objective	Organiser	Timing
Participatory workshop at EU level in Brussels (T.1.2)	European experts of circular economy and sister projects	Identify and discuss good practices and opportunities at the EU level, how they can contribute at the local level and what support they can provide for DECISO	ACR+	M6
National participatory workshop in each pilot (T.1.2)	Local, regional and national stakeholders, possibly relevant EU stakeholders	Identify and discuss good practices and opportunities at the national level, how they can contribute at the local level and what kind of support they can provide for DECISO	Pilot partners/PDM	M8
Mobilisation and learning workshop in each pilot (T.1.3)	Local and regional stakeholders and relevant experts	Report, share and discuss the outcomes of T.1.1 and T.1.2.	Pilot partners/IRRADIARE	TBD
Policy round-table discussion in each pilot (T.2.3)	Regional and national stakeholders and policymakers	Present and discuss results of policy-related analysis and recommendations	Pilot partners/CCDRA	TBD
Review workshop in each pilot (SWOT) (T.3.1)	Pilot working groups, CEE stakeholders	Discuss and validate SWOT analysis and identify competitive elements	Pilot partners/FHH	M16
Review workshop in each pilot (financing schemes) (T.3.2)	Pilot working groups, CEE stakeholders	Discuss and validate financing schemes	Pilot partners/OV	M18

Workshop/Conference and related task	Target group	Objective	Organiser	Timing
Review workshop in each pilot (programmes) (T.3.1)	Pilot working groups, CEE stakeholders	Discuss and validate pilot CE programmes	Pilot partners/FHH	M23
Launch info-day in each pilot (T.4.2)	All SH potentially interested in participating in the programme	Provide information about the programme; more details in GA	Pilot partners/FHH	M22-23
Two annual conferences for wide dissemination (T.5.2)	Stakeholders from EU regions	Dissemination of results; participants to share their experiences, objective, methodologies and practices for CE used, activity results	ACR+	2023 and 2024
Local workshops for dissemination in each pilot area (one at the programme launch, one at the end) (T.5.2)	Stakeholders from pilot regions and countries; experts	Dissemination of results; participants to share their experiences, objectives, methodologies and practices for CE used, activity results	Pilot partners/ACR+	M23 and M36
Two workshops in Brussels for exploitation (T.5.3)	sister projects, local, and national from different regions and EU SH (incl. local public authorities, financial actors, enterprises, and citizens with their organisations)	Define collaboration protocols, establish a Memorandum of Understanding; creation of consensus around the most significant results and best practices from the pilot areas; based on this, define exploitation strategy	ACR+/OV/KOYS	M20 and M26
One workshop in Brussels for scale-up (T.5.4)	Local, national and EU stakeholders	Stimulate a trusted discussion, documenting feedback/uptake and receiving the input from potential replicators for codifying a roadmap that facilitates the replicability and supports the scale-up of good solutions	ACR+/OV/KOYS	M33

Annex 4: Questions to partners (only pilots)

1. Which do you expect to be the most important results from your pilot and/or from pilots in general (please see above KERs for inspiration)?

Please provide a list with the most relevant results expected.

2. Among the above discussed results, which one do you plan or envisage to deploy the most?

Please provide an explanation of the most interesting result to be deployed.

3. Do you have any further suggestion for additional results to be analysed for scaling up into other contexts?

Please provide any suggestions you may have.

4. Are these KERs transferable and replicable in other countries? (I.e. any legislative or environmental or societal conditions that favours your piloting and may be missed in other context or other potential barriers etc)

5. Are these KERS usable by other kinds of organizations? If yes, which? (I.e. specific institutional competencies, etc)

6. Are these KERS adaptable to other sectors, contexts? If yes, which?

7. Which stakeholders in your country/region or EU-wide do you think could use these results, and how? (to answer, please fill the rows in the table below, by matching the results you envisage to exploit with the related stakeholder)

Table of Relevant Stakeholders

WHO will benefit from DECISO results (please add name or category ³)?	Category (please add the abbreviation ⁴)	Which results could they use and how?
other regions/municipalities		
Public utility company		
Financial actors		
Enterprise / consulting		
Policy makers		
Research / Academia		
Citizens / NGO		

8. What do you think would facilitate the use of results for these stakeholders?

Please explain how to engage them.

9. Which barriers could hamper the use of results by the above-mentioned stakeholders?

³ LRA (other regions/municipalities); PU (public utility company) ; F (financial actors); E (enterprises/consulting); P (policy makers); R (Research/Academia); C (citizens/CSO/NGO)

⁴ LRA (other regions/municipalities); PU (public utility company); F (financial actors); E (enterprises/consulting); P (policy makers); R (Research/Academia); C (citizens/CSO/NGO)

Please provide your answer here

10. Do you think there could be any reasons negatively impacting on results' competitiveness or causing their obsolescence?

Please provide your answer here

Annex 5: Questions to stakeholders/potential receivers of key exploitable results (KERs)

Dear participant, your collaboration is precious to provide information about how our results can be useful for your organization. This will enable the first mapping of possible exploitation of our results.

For this reason, we are kindly asking you to answer the following short questionnaire:

1. Name:
2. Email:
3. Full name of your organisation in English and acronym if it exists.
4. Country
- 5. Type of organisation**

other regions/municipalities	Answer
Public utility company	Answer
Financial actors	Answer
Enterprise / consulting	Answer
Policymakers	Answer
Research / Academia	Answer
Citizens / NGO	Answer
Other not mentioned category	Answer

6. What are the topics that your organisation is most related to/interested in?

7. (More than one choice is possible)

- Public infrastructure. Please specify:
- Private business. Please specify:
- Water management. Please specify:
- Waste management. Please specify:
- Public policies. Please specify:
- Other. Please specify:

8. What type of activities are you conducting/following closely?

9. (More than one choice is possible)

10.

Elaboration of new projects/initiatives on CE	Answer Please specify
Management of CE activities	Answer Please specify
Monitoring of CE activities	Answer Please specify
Awareness-raising activities, including education	Answer Please specify
Promotion/implementation/management of environmental policies and strategies	Answer Please specify
Promotion/implementation/management of socio-economic policies and strategies	Answer Please specify
Other	Answer Please specify

8. As part of our activities, we will closely monitor, gather, and evaluate practices/results that are transferable to other contexts. Would you be interested in participating in this process of exploitation of the results from our project? Any affirmative answer does not imply commitment, only an expression of interest.

Yes, on any topic	
Yes, for selected topics	Please specify
Maybe, we will think about it	

Not at all	

9. Do you agree with being included in the list of potential receivers of KERs for receiving information on our result's organization activities?

Yes
No

Annex 6: Social Media Guide

Note: the document related to Social Media Guide will be sent using the email of the EU portal. It is available here: [DECISO Social Media Guide.docx](#)

